

GUNSHOT WOUND OF TEMPORAL BONE: RARE CASE REPORT

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Article Received: 03 May 2025

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Article Revised: 23 May 2025

Department of Pharmacy, Medical Technical Institutes/Kirkuk, Northern

Published on: 13 June 2025

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ABSTRACT

Although temporal bone injuries caused by gunshot wounds are rare but can be disastrous. The high resistance of the temporal bone can often avoid a fatal outcome. The aim of this article was to present a case of a bullet injury to the temporal bone and describe the surgical approach used for treatment. A 55-year-old woman sustained a gunshot wound to the right side of her face, below the lower part of zygoma, penetrating the external ear and mastoid region, with obvious cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) otorrhea. Also she had upper facial nerve palsy. When CSF otorrhea did not improve after 10 days, she was consulted to the ENT team. A CT scan revealed bullet fragments in the lower part of zygoma, as well as two metallic materials in the external auditory canal, the posterior part of the mastoid bone, and a perforated part of the posterior cranial fossa bone. As a result, it was decided to explore the mastoid, remove any shells that were dealing with CSF, and obliteration of mastoid with abdomen fat. The surgery done safely and CSF otorrhea stopped. In conclusion, temporal bone gunshot wounds are uncommon, but need careful managing with otolaryngological surgery team to prevent serious consequences.

KEYWORDS: Temporal bone, zygoma, mastoid bone, auditory canal.

INTRODUCTION

Firearm-related injuries are the major cause of morbidity and mortality in several countries throughout world.[1] Unsurprisingly, gunshot wounds (GS) to the head represent a particularly lethal type of GS, with a mortality rate that exceeds 90%.[2,3] Facial gunshot injuries present as unusual and complex clinical conditions. However, relatively little is known about this condition, particularly temporal bone injury [4]. Extent of this injury depends on several factors, including the distance traveled by the bullet, its type, and its method of penetration [5]. In general, high-energy bullets fired at close range cause the greatest damage [6]. The extent of tissue damage depends on internal lacerations, tissue compression, and temporary cavitation along the bullet's trajectory [7]. The facial area is filled with vital structures in a relatively small space, and a

severe penetrating vascular injury can lead to uncontrolled bleeding, consequently, and death [8]. Although gunshot injuries to the temporal bone are rare, penetrating trauma from these injuries is among the most devastating for vestibule-cochlear and facial nerves function [9].

The high resistance of the temporal bone can sometimes avoid a fatal outcome. However, the complications are in many cases devastating and include hearing loss, facial paralysis, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leak, intracranial damage, and vascular injuries [10]. Surgeons worldwide have reached a consensus regarding the management of facial and neck injuries, including securing the airway, controlling bleeding, identifying other injuries, and preventing additional injuries [11]. There is no doubt that the skill and experience of otolaryngologists minimizes the mortality rate in several critical cases and prevents potential complications in their medical line specialty [12-20]. Management and safe outcomes are challenging, especially when the bullet or its fragments are lodged near vital structures, as bullets penetrating the face tend to migrate away from their original location [21]. This report aims to present a rare case of a woman with GS of the temporal bone and clarify surgical steps in dealing with such cases.

Case presentation

A 55-year-old woman was admitted to neurosurgical unit as a gunshot wound to right side of face with bleeding from the ear. She was treated with a strong antibiotic, but she started to develop CSF otorrhea. Conservative treatment failed to stop CSF otorrhea, so an otolaryngology team was consulted. On examination, the patient was conscious, with a bullet inlet in the lower part of the zygoma, swelling of the external ear and mastoid, and a clear CSF otorrhea without obvious exit of the bullet. She was also accompanied by upper facial nerve paralysis, and the lower part was normal, as shown in Figure (1).

Figure 1: Clinical signs of the patient during examination.

The CT scan revealed scattered metallic parts of the bullet spread across the lower part of zygoma, one lodged in the external ear, and another large one in posterior section of mastoid that penetrating the area of posterior cranial fossa as in shown in figure (2). The middle ear ossicles and inner ear were intact; hence the decision was made to investigate the mastoid with a more posterior skin incision, to deal with excessive bleeding or CSF otorrhea.

Figure 2: CT scan shows penetrating bullet to mastoid.

Surgical steps

Under general anesthesia, endotracheal intubation, sterilization, and patient covering, we began with a lateral skull base incision, which is more posterior than the typical post-auricular incision, to control any bleeding from the sigmoid sinus or profuse CSF rhinorrhea that may occur. After incision of the subcutaneous tissue and elevation of the periosteum, we noticed a vertical fracture in the mastoid bone and began drilling the mastoid bone fully to expose this area completely. It was subsequently observed that a part of the bullet had been shattered and removed. After exposing the external auditory canal anteriorly, we passed into another portion of the bullet. During surgery, a slight CSF leak was observed, and no bleeding occurred. Abdominal fat was then proceeded to obliterate the mastoid cavity. Using a microscope, all granulation tissue was removed from the external auditory canal, and the tympanic membrane was intact. A tube approximately 3 mm in diameter was then inserted into the external canal to prevent stenosis. The wound was sutured in multiple layers as shown in Figure (3) .

Figure 3: Surgical steps, from lateral skull base incision to suturing the wound.

DISCUSSION

A rare case of penetrating bullet injury to the facial bone is presented, and represent a critical case where removing a bullet stuck in the face to prevent potentially fatal complications is more complex than in other parts of the body [22]. The bullet can be lethal at a range of up to 200 meters, and injuries are usually characterized by strong energy transfer [23]. The injured patient was well within this range, as demonstrated by her complete individual injury history.

The typical appearance of bullet entry wounds is a bruise, sloppy skin, and a faint or crusty bruise. The skin wound typically has a worn edge and is a puncture wound [24]. In general, the most close-range injuries of facial bone from gunshot have a severe impact on the soft tissues, and the first-line management includes stabilization of the airway and circulation. After intubating the patient and verifying that there is no major vascular injury, attention can be concentrated on the otoneurological damage [25]. A previous systematic review on ballistic injury of the temporal bone has stated hearing loss in 62% of cases, facial nerve weakness

in 48%, intracranial injury (stroke, hematoma, infection, carotid cavernous fistula, or carotid artery injury) in 43%, vascular injury in 25%, and CSF leak in 12% [26]. This case presented with upper facial nerve palsy and CSF otorrhea, thus indications for early surgical intervention included facial paralysis and a cerebrospinal fluid otorrhea. The CSF leak must be treated aggressively due to the risk of intracranial infection such as meningitis [27]. In this case, intravenous antibiotics for meningitis were initiated immediately after the identification of the presence of a CSF leak, and surgery was performed 10 days when the conservative management failed to stop CSF otorrhea. During surgery, bone and squamous epithelium fragments were removed to prevent cholesteatoma; the foreign body was removed to prevent secondary infection, and the cavity was closed using abdominal fat to treat the persistent CSF leak and prevent meningitis.

CONCLUSIONS

Gunshot temporal bone injury is a life-threatening condition and need careful managements with perfect surgical steps to prevent serious complications.

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